

Reaction of rice cultivars to bacterial blight, blast, and *Helminthosporium* leaf spot under natural conditions. Punjab, India.

Cross combination	Selections (no.)	Reaction to disease			
		Bacterial blight ^a		Blast ^b at Gurdaspur	<i>Helminthosporium</i> leaf spot ^c at Gurdaspur
		Kapurthala	Gurdaspur		
Basmati 370/Jaya	54	1.7	2.5	2.8	3.5
Norin 18/Hyb 27	52	0.8	2.0	4.7	3.3
Mutants of Basmati 370	33	1.3	2.2	2.1	3.0
Basmati 370/Hamsa	22	1.2	2.2	4.0	3.1
Basmati 370/IR127-80-1-10	5	1.6	2.6	2.4	2.2
IRB/Basmati 370	4	0.7	2.0	3.0	2.5
Phulpattas 72/Mut 65	4	1.7	2.7	2.5	3.5
Basmati 370/IR8	3	1.0	1.7	3.0	2.7
Hyb 27/Mut 65	2	3.5	3.5	2.5	4.5
Mut 52/Basmati 370	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
Basmati 370/IR480-5	1	1.0	1.0	3.0	5.0
UPR71-12	1	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
UPR71-21	1	3.0	2.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-4	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
UPR70/30-7	1	2.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-14	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
UPR70/30-15	1	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
UPR70/30-25	1	3.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
UPR70/30-26	1	0	3.0	3.0	5.0
UPR70/30-39	1	3.0	3.0	2.0	3.0
Jaya	—	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.7
PR106	—	1.3	1.7	2.0	3.0
Palman 579	—	2.0	2.3	1.7	3.0
Basmati 370	—	1.3	2.7	1.7	3.0

^a0 = no infection (immune); 1 = 1–1% of leaf area infected (moderately resistant); 2 = 11–25% (moderately susceptible); 3 = 26–50% (susceptible); 4 = more than 50% infection (highly susceptible).

^bRated only at Gurdaspur. 1 = immune, 2 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 4 = susceptible, 5 = 50% of leaves infected, 6 = 75% of leaves infected, 7 = 100% of leaves infected.

^cRated only at Gurdaspur. 1 = highly resistant, 2 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 4 = moderately susceptible, 5 = susceptible, 6 = very susceptible.

and the cultivar PR106 were moderately resistant to bacterial blight. Palman 579 and Basmati 370 were resistant to blast.

Most of the rices gave resistant to moderately resistant reactions to *Helminthosporium* leaf spot. **W**

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Reaction of rice breeding lines to bacterial blight

P. Varadarajan Nair and K. M. Rajan, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Alleppey, Kerala, India

Bacterial blight of rice incited by *Xanthomonas oryzae* is a serious disease in Kuttanad tract of Kerala, India. Forty-one advanced promising rice cultures developed at the Rice Research Station, Moncompu, were artificially inoculated with a viable and fresh bacterial suspension to study their reactions to bacterial blight. The IRRI leaf clipping method was adapted to the greenhouse for the study. Twelve cultures recorded disease scores below 4: M24-179-1, M24-39-1, M23-57-2-1, M23-17-1-2, M23-33-2-1, M23-57-1-2, M23-83-1-1-2, M23-33-3-1, M23-9-1-1, M23-73-1-1-2, M13-116-1, and M23-16-1-1. **W**

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Feeding of brown planthopper on rice varieties labeled with ³²P

P. C. Lippold, J. O. Lee, Y. H. Kim, S. J. Park, J. Ryu, K. H. Chung, M. D. Davis, and K. Steenberg, Crop Improvement Research Center and Institute of Agricultural Science, Office of Rural Development, Suweon 170, and Korean Atomic Energy Research Institute, Seoul, Korea

The importance of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*

has increased in recent years in the Republic of Korea. A 1975 BPH outbreak was especially severe because unusually warm summer temperatures caused a generation advance (BPH do not overwinter in Korea; they migrate annually in late spring and early summer from the Asian mainland).

The use of radioisotopes to complement conventional screening and evaluation of new breeding lines and varieties was investigated in 1976. In

initial trials, three varieties that differed widely in BPH resistance in conventional trials were evaluated by radiotracer methods. The varieties were Yushin, a new high yielding variety; Jinheung, an indigenous japonica; and IR747, a BPH-resistant line.

Six 10-day-old seedlings of each variety were wrapped lightly with a band of absorbent cotton and inserted in 1.27-cm (1/2-inch) holes in a stainless steel plate. The plate was suspended over a

tray containing $^{32}\text{P}\text{-H}_3\text{PO}_4$ (at a concentration of 0.5 c/ml) in distilled water. The solution level in the tray was high enough to cover most of the seedlings' root area. After 24 hours, the seedlings were transferred to a tray containing only distilled water and then infested with female and male BPH adults that had received no food or water for 3 hours.

The insects were allowed to feed for 24 hours, then were placed in a freezer to kill them. They were placed on a 1.27-cm strip of doublestick cellophane tape affixed to the bottom of a 0.32- × 3.18-cm (1/8 × 1-1/4 in.) aluminum planchet and counted with an Aloka Model TDC-6 scaler.

The female BPH on Yushin seedlings were the most active feeders as indicated by the number of radioactive counts/minute (Table 1). Feeding was intermediate on the japonica Jinheung and lower on the resistant IR747. Female feeding was always higher than that of the male.

In a more extensive trial, eight varieties, each with six replicate seedlings per tray, were compared. The concentration of ^{32}P was 0.43 μC Na_2HPO_4 /ml of water solution. Seedlings were placed in the ^{32}P solution for 24 hours followed by replacement of the ^{32}P solution with plain distilled water. One pair of adult BPH per plant was allowed to feed for 24 hours and then anesthetized with ethyl acetate. The insects were prepared as before and then

Table 1. Radioactive counts^a of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* fed on rice varieties labeled with ^{32}P . Republic of Korea

Variety	Reaction ^b to brown planthopper	Brown planthopper	
		Sex	Counts (no.) ^c
Yushin	S	Female	1898 a
		Male	842 b
Jinheung	S	Female	336 bc
		Male	180 c
IR747	R	Female	168 c
		Male	17 c

^aBased on av. of 5 replicates corrected for background.

^bR = resistant; S = susceptible.

^cAny two means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Table 2. Counts^a of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* on rice varieties labeled with ^{32}P . Republic of Korea.

Variety	Reaction to BPH ^b	Radioactive counts/minute		Count ratio	Relative count of females (%)
		Females	Males		
Tongil	S	19,765	3,129	6.32	100.0
Yushin	S	14,214	2,056	6.91	71.9
Milyang 30	MR-R	4,364	292	14.95	22.1
Jinheung	S	4,321	620	6.97	21.9
IR747	R	1,394	172	8.10	7.1
ASD 7	R	1,188	306	3.88	6.0
Suweon 264	MS	1,098	408	2.69	5.6
Mudgo	R	789	934	0.84	4.0

^aAv. of 6 counts/sex per variety, corrected for background.

^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

counted with a Tracerlab Versamatic 11 Scaler.

The highest counts were for BPH that fed on Tongil and Yushin varieties (Table 2). These two varieties, which now grow on about 60% of Korea's rice land, were injured somewhat during the 1975 BPH epidemic. But because they matured earlier, they suffered less injury than the local japonica. The resistance of the newer selections Milyang 30 and Suweon 264 is promising. Again differences in the counts of female and male insects, expressed as a ratio, were significant. Only on Mudgo, which is resistant to BPH biotype 1, were counts

of males higher than counts of females, but the difference was not significant. (The presence of BPH biotypes has not been observed in Korea.) Assuming a relative preference of 100% for Tongil, the relative counts of females matched the results of conventional varietal screening tests perfectly (Table 2).

Additional trials include other leafhopper and planthopper species. Radiotracers not only facilitate resistance screening but could conceivably be used in the analysis of biotypes and in tests requiring quantitative assessment of insect activity.

Field reaction of rices to the brown planthopper and ragged stunt virus

E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, and V. Viajante, research assistant, International Rice Research Institute

The incidence of ragged stunt virus, transmitted by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, has been high at IRRI since late 1976. In 1977, three experiments were conducted to determine the field resistance of the IR varieties, breeding lines, and entries in the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) to BPH and ragged stunt.

In all experiments, the BPH population was promoted by spraying susceptible border plants surrounding the test entries with synthetic pyrethroids, cypermethrin, or

decamethrin (see article in this issue for details).

The following IR rices evaluated in the field at IRRI were resistant to BPH and had low ragged stunt incidence (less than 17% of hills infested): IR32, IR2863-38-1-2, IR4432-52-6-4, IR4432-103-6-4, IR4570-83-3-3-2, and IR5853-118-3. IR29 had 76% and 100% of hills infested in two experiments. IR32 is resistant and IR29 is susceptible to biotype 2 of the BPH, currently considered the predominant biotype at IRRI. In greenhouse tests these breeding lines are resistant to the three biotypes of BPH. All have CR94-13 (PTB18/PTB21//IR8) as a common resistant parent, except IR4570-83-3-3-2 which has PTB18 in its ancestry.

Evaluation of the 1977 IRBPHN indicated that varieties such as PTB19,